

LABORATORY JOURNAL

ELECTROCHEMICAL OXIDATION KINETICS OF LIGNOCELLULOSE FRACTIONS

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15/03/2023 – The test rig

Objective

Get to know the setup by drawing it and flowing water inside. Clean the setup to get it ready.

Scheme of the setup

Dimensions of the Nickel electrodes

21/03/2023 – ST-001-NiNi-BL - Step test for raw BL, Ni/Ni cell

Objective

Get to know the setup, figure how the software works, figure at what Voltage the current is stable.

Parameters

Reservoir : raw BL

Oil : Diethylene glycol

Cell : 2 Ni electrodes, from one of Francisco's Step test. 2 Teflon pieces.

Sequence : Francisco's sequence

- Duration : 2.5 hours
- Range : 1 to 2.5 Volts, with step of 0.25 Volts (20 min each)
- Sets : 0.02 Volts, 1 Amp

Comments

No problem during the experiment. GC not connected yet.

Samples

1 sample at the end of the run. To be analyzed in GPC

Results

(see the figure opposite)

Conclusion

No stable region was detected in this range of Voltage, and with this setup. Hence it is decided that next experiment should have a broader range of higher Voltage and diluted BL in the reservoir.

22/03/2023 – ST-002-NiNi-BL1-1W - Step test for BL diluted with water, Ni/Ni cell

Objective

- Dilute the BL with water to see if that makes a better depolymerization of lignin.
- Figure at what Voltage the current is stable for BL diluted with water.

Parameters

Reservoir : BL diluted with distilled water (1:1), 40 mL

Oil : Silicon oil thermofluid (supports the heat better)

Cell : 2 Ni electrodes, from one of Francisco's Step test. 2 Teflon pieces.

Sequence : New sequence ("Step test V2")

- Duration : 3 hours
- Range : 1 to 3 Volts, with step of 0.25 Volts (20 min each)
- Sets : 0.02 Volts, 1 Amp

Comments

- **Leakage** problems. Solved by tightening the screws more with the clamp and with the cell configuration drawn above.

- When the sequence is started, the current is about 1 A and the voltage doesn't go higher than about 0,03 V. That means there is a **shortcut** in the circuit. The cell is observed and a contact between the cathode and the metallic part of the cell is detected. The sequence is stopped.

Samples

None

Results

None

Conclusion

The electrodes need to be redesigned to allow the passage of the current without a shortcut. A new cathode is to be tested, with the two holes oriented in a perpendicular way to how they were, that way the electrodes can be placed perpendicularly to the inlet/outlet of BL and avoid the shortcut.

23/03/2023 – ST-003-NiNi-BL1-1W - Step test for BL diluted with water, Ni/Ni cell

Objective

- Dilute the BL with **water** to see if that makes a better depolymerization of lignin.
- Figure at what Voltage the current is stable for BL diluted with water.
- Test out the **new electrode design** for the cathode to see if it prevents shortcuts.

Parameters

Reservoir : BL diluted with distilled water (1:1), 40 mL, Pump : 8.5 V

Oil : Silicon oil thermofluid (supports the heat better)

Cell : 2 Ni electrodes : anode from Francisco's Step test, cathode from the workshop. 2 Teflon pieces.

Sequence : New sequence ("Step test V2")

- Duration : 3 hours
- Range : 1 to 3 Volts, with step of 0.25 Volts (20 min each)
- Sets : 0.02 Volts, 1 Amp

Comments

No leakage with the new electrode. No shortcut. A lot of deposit on the Nickel anode.

Sample

1 at the end of the experiment
→ analyzed in GPC and GC

Results

(See the figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The new electrode design works well.
- The current is stable from 2 to 3 V.
- The GPC shows that there isn't a lot of monomers in the final sample. It is decided to take from now on a sample at 0, 2 and 3 V to see a bit clearer when the monomers are formed.

27/03/2023 - ST-004-NiNi-BL1-1WL - Step test for BL diluted with white liquor, Ni/Ni cell

Objective

- Dilute the BL with **white liquor** to see if that makes a better depolymerization of lignin.
- Figure at what Voltage the current is stable for BL diluted with WL.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 20 mL WL prepared a week earlier)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 1 A then 3 A

Comments

During the experiment, the current max. is set to 3 A because the current reached the limit of 1 A. This is because the WL contains many salts that are very conductive.

Samples

1 sample before the sequence and 1 after. Both analyzed in GC and GPC.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- To be tested now to dilute BL : glycerol, phenol, butanol.
- The current is stable from 1,5 to 2 V.

28/03/2023 - ST-005-NiNi-BL1-1GLY - Step test for BL diluted with glycerol, Ni/Ni cell

Objective

- Dilute the BL with **glycerol** to see if that makes a better depolymerization of lignin.
- Figure at what Voltage the current is stable for BL diluted with GLY.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 20 mL Glycerol)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Comments

None

Samples

1 at 2.25 V, analyzed in GPC and GC

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is stable from 1.75 to 2 V.

29/03/2023 - ST-006-NiNi-BL2-1W-1WL - Step test for BL diluted with W and WL

Objective

- Dilute the BL with **water and white liquor** to see if that makes a better depolymerization of lignin and if the current is stable but lower than with just WL.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 10 mL Water + 10 mL WL)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 3 A

Comments

None

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Analyzed in GPC and GC

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is stable at 2 and 2.25 V.
- At 2.5 and 2.75 V, the current is not very stable and it decreases.
- There is a current drop at 3 V.

30/03/2023 - ST-007-NiNi-BL1-1GLY - Step test for BL diluted with glycerol, Ni/Ni cell

Objective

- Redo this experiment but collect a sample at 0, 2 and 3 V this time for more results.
- Dilute the BL with **glycerol** to see if that makes a better depolymerization of lignin.
- Figure at what Voltage the current is stable for BL diluted with GLY.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 20 mL Glycerol)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Comments

None

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V. Analyzed in GPC and GC

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is stable for 1.75 and 2 V.
- First good MS results where we can see a blob for glycerin, for benzene and dimethanol.

12/04/2023 - ST-008-NiNi-BL - Step test for BL

Objective

- Redo this experiment but collect a sample at 0, 2 and 3 V this time for more results and use the sequence that goes up to 3V.
- Figure at what Voltage the current is stable for BL.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL BL

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 1 A

Comments

None

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is very unstable around 2 V, not very stable overall and very low.

13/04/2023 - ST-009-NiNi-BL1-1WL - Step test for BL diluted with WL

Objective

- Redo this experiment but set the highest Amps value at 3.5 Amps to not be limited when the current reaches a high value.
- Figure at what Voltage the current is stable for BL diluted with WL.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 10 mL Water + 10 mL WL)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 3 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 140°C

Treal (bottle) = 94.0°C

Comments

Foam is observed in the reservoir.

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

GC and GPC runs.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is stable at 2 and 2.25 V then decreases a bit. Most stable around 2.25 V.

19/04/2023 – Comparing the chronoamperometry step tests ST-001 to ST-009

Stability of the current

The most stable current regions are 2 and 2.25 V.

Influence of the dilution of BL

Dilution effectively tends to reduce polymers and increase monomers

Influence of the Voltage (HPLC, RID)

For each solvent, it is the same curve for 2 and 3V. For BL:W:WL, the monomers decrease. For glycerol, there is a high peak in monomers.

Influence of the solvent (HPLC, RID)

There is the same amount of monomers between 20 and 23 minutes for the 3 solvents, at each voltage

GPC results (DAD) for every mixture, at 2V:

GPC results (DAD) for BL:WL (1:1):

GPC results (DAD) for BL:W:WL (2:1:1):

GPC results (DAD) for BL:Glycerol (1:1):

GC results (FID) for BL:WL (1:1):

GC results (FID) for BL:W:WL (2:1:1):

GC results (FID) for BL:GLY (1:1):

GC results (MS) for BL:W:WL (2:1:1):

GC results (MS) for BL:GLY (1:1):

17/04/2023 – NiOOH-001 – NiOOH electrode preparation test 1

Objective

- Prepare a Ni electrode with a black NiOOH deposit, using a current density of 0.5 mA/cm²

Parameters

Electrolyte : 150 mL in a becher. Containing : 0.05M NiSO₄, 0.1M NaCOOCH₃, 0.005M NaOH.

- Preparation : Dissolve these 3 components in water. The solution is blue-green.
- Masses for 250 mL of solution :

$$m(\text{NiSO}_4) = 3.32 \text{ g} \quad m(\text{NaCOOCH}_3) = 2.05 \text{ g} \quad m(\text{NaOH}) = 0.048 \text{ g}$$

Electrodes : both Nickel. Cathode contains 2 holes, Anode is plain. No stirring.

Sequence : “NiOOH electrode preparation”

- Duration : 12 x 60s with 5s break in each → 12 min total
- Voltage : To have a current density of 0.5 mA/cm², with the electrode being 3 cm², that makes 1.5*2= 3 mA (front and back of the electrode). To obtain 3 mA, it is necessary to apply 1.5 V.

Comments

The anode is connected to the red wire (R) and the cathode to the black wire (B) to have the deposit formed on the anode.

Results

- During the sequence, the current is about 3 mA.
- Very thin deposit layer on the anode. Non uniform (circular shape).
- No deposit on the cathode, as planned.

Conclusion

- Need to re-do this experiment with a higher voltage or longer steps to have a darker and thicker deposit.
- Need to try stirring for a more uniform shape of the deposit on the anode.

18/04/2023 – NiOOH-002 – NiOOH electrode preparation test 2

Objective

- Prepare a Ni electrode with a thicker black NiOOH deposit

Parameters

Electrolyte : Same as previous experiment (NiOOH-001)

Electrodes : both Nickel, plain (without holes)

Sequence : “NiOOH electrode preparation”

- Duration : 12 x 60s with 5s break in each → 12 min total
- Voltage : 2.35 V

Stirring : 180 rpm

Comments

The cathode has a thin layer deposit too.

Results

- During the sequence, the current is about 13 mA which makes a current density of 2.2 mA/cm².
- Uniform deposit on both of the electrodes. Still not thick enough on the anode.

Conclusion

- Need to re-do this experiment with a higher voltage or longer steps to have a darker and thicker deposit on the anode.

18/04/2023 – NiOOH-003 – NiOOH electrode preparation test 3

Objective

- Prepare a Ni electrode with a thicker black NiOOH deposit

Parameters

Electrolyte : Same as previous experiment (NiOOH-002)

Electrodes : both Nickel, plain (without holes), same as previously

Sequence : “NiOOH electrode preparation”

- Duration : [12 x 60s with 5s break in each] then repeat → 24 min in total
- Voltage : 2.35 V

Stirring : 180 rpm

Results

- During the sequence, the current is about 13 mA which makes a current density of 2.2 mA/cm².
- Dark deposit on the anode.

Conclusion

- **Good result**, the layer seems dark/thick enough.
- To be tested in the cell for a chronoamperometry step test to determine if it makes a better depolymerization of lignin.
- The sequence can be optimized for a shorter time.

18/04/2023 – NiOOH-004 – NiOOH electrode preparation test 4

Objective

- Prepare a Ni electrode with a thicker black NiOOH deposit

Parameters

Electrolyte : Same as previous experiment (NiOOH-002)

Electrodes : both Nickel, plain (without holes), same as previously

Sequence : “NiOOH electrode preparation”

- Duration : 8 x 100s with 10s break in each → 14 min total
- Voltage : 2.35 V

Stirring : 200 rpm

Comments

None

Results

- During the sequence, the current is about 15 mA which makes a current density of 2.5 mA/cm².
- Some deposit on the anode.

Conclusion

- The NiOOH layer is not very thick. Not enough deposit.

20/04/2023 - ST-010-NiNiOOH-BL2-1W-1WL - Step test for NiOOH anode

Objective

- See if using a NiOOH anode instead of a regular Ni anode changes the results.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 10 mL Water + 10 mL WL)

Cell : Ni cathode, NiOOH anode (prepared in the NiOOH electrode preparation test 3)

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 3 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 142°C

Treal (bottle) = 93.5°C

Comments

Foam is observed in the reservoir, thus stirring is slowed down from the usual 400 rpm to 290 rpm.

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V. GC and GPC runs.

Results

- Between 1 and 2 V, the current is unstable.
- At 2 V, the current is stable.
- Higher than 2 V, it decreases during the step and a current drop is observed during the 2.75 V step.

Comparison to regular raw Ni anode

GC-MS results: not identified

GPC results

Conclusion

- The current is only stable around 2 V, and less stable than without the Nickel Oxide layer on the anode, especially above 2.5V.
- It is not necessary to apply a NiOOH deposit layer on the electrode before the run.

21/04/2023 - ST-011-NiNi-BL2-1,5W-0,5WL - Step test for BL diluted with W and WL

Objective

- Redo this experiment with a different ratio (previous was 2:1:1 and here it's 2:1,5:0,5) to see the influence of the ratio
- Verify the trend that with more WL, the current is higher

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 15 mL Water + 5 mL WL)

Pump Speed : 8.50 V

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 3 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 146°C

Treal (bottle) = 93.5°C

Stirring : 350 rpm

Comments

The temperature inside the bottle was too high (>100°C) so the water evaporated and the BL became too thick and stained the tubings. The bath temperature was then set to 140°C.

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite and figure at the following page)

- Current drop above 2.5 V.

Conclusion

- The current is stable at 2 and 2.25 V then decreases a bit. Most stable around 2 V.
- The tubings need to be replaced for a better flow and a thorough control of the temperature needs to be operated to avoid boiling up the water contained in the BL.

24/04/2023 - Comparison of the step tests for different ratios of BL:W:WL

03/05/2023 - ST-012-BL2-0,75W-0,75WL-0,5GLY - Step test with alcohol : Glycerol

Objective

- Combine the effects of the WL and an alcohol (here: glycerol) to try and obtain both a high current and a depolymerization of the lignin.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7,5 mL Water + 7,5 mL WL + 5,0 mL Glycerol)

New tubings (clear flow)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 3 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 134°C

Treal (bottle) = 94.0°C

Comments

Foam is observed in the reservoir. The Tset of the bath is reduced to 125°C.

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is most stable at 2V.

04/05/2023 - ST-013-BL2-0,75W-0,75WL-0,5BU - Step test with alcohol : Butanol

Objective

- Combine the effects of the WL and an alcohol (here: butanol) to try and obtain both a high current and a depolymerization of the lignin.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7,5 mL Water + 7,5 mL WL + 5,0 mL Butanol)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-3 V
- Sets : 0.02 V, 3 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 124°C

Treal (bottle) = 87.0°C

Comments

As soon as the bath temperature reaches 117°C, the bottle temperature rapidly increases to 97°C. That makes the water boil and the vapors prevent the BL from being pumped into the tubes.

Hence the Tset of the bath is reduced to 115°C and the experiment is carried out at 80°C.

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is most stable at 2V.

08/05/2023 – HPLC analysis of monomers - Set up of a new column

Objective

- Be able to detect different monomers in the BL samples to track depolymerization better.

Column

The column is described in a paper (Klaus Fischer and Susanne Höffler, “RP-HPLC Analysis of Phenolic Lignin Monomers with DAD and Coulometric Array Detection, 2020) that analyzes lignin monomers. It is a Kinetex C18 RP column (100 x 3 mm, particle size 2.6 µm), equipped with a guard column. It is mounted as column 1 in the HPLC system and flushed with the initial solvent mix for some hours before running the first sample.

Method

According to the previously cited paper, the following method was written in ChemStation software:

Name	CHLOE_LIGNIN_2.M
Solvent	Mix of A (formic acid in water, 0.15 M, pH 2.27) and B (formic acid in methanol, 0.15 M) :
Gradient	(i) 0–20 min: isocratic: 90% A, 10% B, (ii) 20–35 min: linear gradient from 90 to 75% A (iii) 35–40 min: linear gradient from 75 to 50% A (iv) 40-42 min : linear gradient from 50 to 90% A
Acquisition time	40 min (+ 2 min setting initial solvent)
Flow rate	0.4 mL/min (Constant)
Temperature	40°C
Injection volume	5 µL
Wash vial	92 (mix of initial solvent ratio: A:B (90:10))
DAD	230 nm
RID	None
Average pressure	195 bar
Maximum pressure	400 bar

Comments

There was some trouble testing the new method because the pressure was building up in the column until it reached the security level (400 bar) which stopped the run automatically.

The injection volume was initially 100 µL and was reduced to 5 µL but that did not solve this pressure problem. It was found that the flow rate was 1 mL/min in the table of the solvents, which caused the pressure to build up. This was hence reduced to 0.4 mL/min for every step of the gradient of solvents.

Conclusion

- The column has been setup successfully.

11/05/2023 – Testing the new column - Separation of phenolic compounds

Objective

- Verify the detection of monomers and compare their peak to the ones in the paper.

Parameters

The column was tested with a mix of different phenolic reference compounds found in the table below:

# peak	Compound	Full name	Structure	Mass (mg)	Concentration (mg/L)	Danger
4	Vanillic acid	4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzoic acid		5,6	11,2	-
6	Vanillin	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde		41,2	82,4	-
7	Syringic acid	4-Hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxybenzoic acid		5,0	10	-
11	Benzoic acid	Benzenecarboxylic acid		10,3	20,6	CMR
12	Salicylic acid	2-Hydroxybenzoic acid		12,1	24,2	-
15	PHBA	4-hydroxybenzoic acid		12,1	24,2	-

A first mix containing all of the above compounds was analyzed as 'ref mix 1' and another one without the compound #15 (4-hydroxybenzoic acid) as 'ref mix 2'.

Results

The DAD (230nm) peaks were attributed, with a certainty for the peak of compound #15.

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The monomers are effectively separated in the column and elude in the studied range.

15/05/2023 – Analyzing samples from ST-006 experiment in the new HPLC column

Objective

- Find a way to prepare BL samples for the new column
- Analyze them to see what peaks are obtained

Parameters

The solvent used is the initial mix of A and B (90:10) first used in the method. The samples are from an experiment that gave promising results for depolymerization: ST-006-NiNi-BL2-1W-1WL (0 and 2V).

Preparation of the samples

It is observed that the lignin precipitates when adding the solvent. Hence different ratios of the sample/solvent were tested to elaborate a sample that does not precipitate once it mixes with the eluent in the column (to not clog it). The following protocol was made for preparing a sample:

- Take 0.03 g of sample and add 1.23 g of solvent (ratio 20:80). It precipitates. (pH = 3)
- Filter it to remove the precipitate.
- Mix 0.03 g of the obtained sample with 1.23 g of solvent. No precipitate is formed (pH = 2)

Results

The mix of BL-W-WL has the same peaks as ST-006-0V.

After running the power for some time, at 2V, the peaks obtained are a little different (they have an offset).

Conclusion

- The BL sample is successfully diluted in the mix of solvents (A:B)
- The amount of peaks has not changed between 0 and 2 V but the monomers are eluted quickly after 2V.

16/05/2023 – Comparing the chronoamperometry step tests of BL:W:WL:Alcohol

Results

At this point, the different alcohols have given the following results:

Conclusion

Using a different alcohol seem to impact the current very little.

Hence it is decided to carry on step tests with a long time at 2.25 V for the following experiments, and not go up to 3 V, in order to study the stability of the current during a longer time to detect the best alcohol.

The new voltage sequence is as follow:

- From 1 to 2.25 V
- Step: 0.25 V
- Total: 3h

Steps: 20 min each and 80 min last step

22/05/2023 - ST-014-BL2-0,75W-0,75WL-0,5PRO - Step test with alcohol : 1-Propanol

Objective

- Combine the effects of the WL and an alcohol (here: 1-propanol) to try and obtain both a high current and a depolymerization of the lignin.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7,6 mL Water + 7,5 mL WL + 5,0 mL 1-Propanol)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 118°C

Treal (bottle) = 81.7 then 83.1°C

Comments

None

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is stable at 2 and 2.25 V and reaches a high current (1 A) at 2.25 V.
- During the 80 min step at 2.25 V, the current decreases a little but stays overall constant.

23/05/2023 - ST-015-BL2-0,75W-0,75WL-0,5EtOH - Step test with alcohol : Ethanol

Objective

- Combine the effects of the WL and an alcohol (here: Ethanol) to try and obtain both a high current and a depolymerization of the lignin.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7,6 mL Water + 7,5 mL WL + 5,0 mL Ethanol)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 108°C

Treal (bottle) = 75.3°C

Comments

None

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is stable at 2 and 2.25 V and reaches a high current (0.82 A) at 2.25 V.
- During the 80 min step at 2.25 V, the current stays constant.
- The current is more constant than with Propanol but a just bit lower. (0.82 A vs 1 A)

24/05/2023 - ST-016-BL2-0,75W-0,75WL-0,5MeOH - Step test with alcohol : Methanol

Objective

- Combine the effects of the WL and an alcohol (here: Methanol) to try and obtain both a high current and a depolymerization of the lignin.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7,6 mL Water + 7,5 mL WL + 5,0 mL Methanol)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 85°C

Treal (bottle) = 63.5°C

Comments

None

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is stable at 2 and 2.25 but decreases a bit over time.
- The current is less constant than with Propanol and Ethanol and a bit lower.

30/05/2023 - ST-017-BL2-0,75W-0,75WL-0,5Ph - Step test with alcohol : Phenol

Objective

- Combine the effects of the WL and an alcohol (here: Phenol) to try and obtain both a high current and a depolymerization of the lignin.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7,6 mL Water + 7,5 mL WL + 5,0 mL Phenol)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 90°C

Treal (bottle) = 64.4°C

Comments

- Shortcut and leak problems. The cell is cleaned opened and cleaned and the problems are solved.
- Very big deposit on the anode after the experiment.

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

Phenol is not a good choice for this experiment because:

- it is a solid and it clogs the cell, hence creating leaks and shortcuts.
- the current is very low
- it creates a lot of deposit and unstability around 1.5 V

31/05/2023 - ST-018-BL2-0,75W-0,75WL-0,5GLY - Step test with alcohol : Glycerol

Objective

- Combine the effects of the WL and an alcohol (here: Glycerol) to try and obtain both a high current and a depolymerization of the lignin.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7,6 mL Water + 7,5 mL WL + 5,0 mL Glycerol)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 90°C

Treal (bottle) = 65.5°C

Comments

None

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is stable at 2 and 2.25 and stays constant during the whole experiment.
- Each step, the current takes a bit more time to stabilize because glycerol is visquous.

01/06/2023 - ST-019-BL2-0,75W-0,75WL-0,5Bu- Step test with alcohol : Butanol

Objective

- Combine the effects of the WL and an alcohol (here: Butanol) to try and obtain both a high current and a depolymerization of the lignin.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7,6 mL Water + 7,5 mL WL + 5,0 mL Butanol)

Cell : Same as before but using a raw Ni anode.

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 90°C

Treal (bottle) = 59.5°C

Comments

The Temperature suddenly increased to 86°C in the bottle, hence the T of the bath was reduced to 82.8°C to carry out the end of the experiment (2 and 2.25 V steps) which resulted in 61.3°C in the bottle.

Samples

1 at 0, 2 and 3V.

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is unstable from 1.5 to 2.25 V and the temperature increased brutally again, hence Butanol is not a good choice.

02/06/2023 – Comparing the chronoamperometry step tests of BL:W:WL:Alcohol

Recap of the different alcohols tested and their boiling point (bp)

Alcohol	State at room T	bp (°C)	Structure
Glycerol	liquid	290	<chem>OCC(O)CO</chem>
1-Butanol	liquid	117,7	<chem>CCCCO</chem>
Propan-1-ol	liquid	97	<chem>CCCO</chem>
Ethanol	liquid	78,2	<chem>CCO</chem>
Phenol	solid	182	<chem>Oc1ccccc1</chem>
Methanol	liquid	64,7	<chem>CO</chem>

Results

With the new sequence, the different alcohols have given the following results:

1-Propanol and Ethanol seem to be the best options because they offer the highest and most stable currents.

Their samples are analyzed in GPC and GC:

BL: W: WL: Propanol (GPC)

BL: W: WL: Ethanol (GPC)

BL: W: WL: Propanol (GC-MS)

BL: W: WL: Ethanol (GC-MS)

Conclusion

- **GPC:** the 0V samples have strange graphs, hence it is decided to clean the sample valve better after each experiment. The GPC graph don't give a lot of information so it is decided to analyze these samples in the new HPLC column and compare them to raw toluene signal.
- **GC-MS:** monomers are formed (toluene). The other blobs are not dark enough to be attributed correctly. It is decided to try to pass these samples through a resin and derivatize them before the GC.

30/06/2023 - ST-020-NiCu - Step test with Copper cathode

Objective

- See if using a copper cathode instead of the nickel cathode can lead to a more stable current or a better depolymerization
- Obtain less deposit with diluted BL than with copper cathode and undiluted BL

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 10 mL Water + 10 mL WL)

Cell : raw Ni anode, raw Cu cathode

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 135°C

Treal (bottle) = 90.3°C

Comments

A lot of deposit is observed on the cathode at the end of the reaction.

Samples

0V, 2V, tf

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- The current is stable around 2V but unstable above.
- At 2.25V, the current drops and a big deposit occurs on the cathode.
- Copper doesn't seem like a good choice, even with diluted BL, at 2.25V.
- To be tested for a longer run at 2V.

03/07/2023 - ST-021-NiNi - Step test with Nickel cathode

Objective

- Compare to the previous experience, using nickel instead of copper with the exact same sequence.
- Verify the stability of the current with a Nickel cathode on a long run at 2.25V.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 10 mL Water + 10 mL WL)

Cell : raw Ni anode, raw Ni cathode

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 135°C

Treal (bottle) = 90.3°C

Comments

None

Samples

0V, 2V, tf

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- Very stable current, moderately high (lower than with Copper cathode)
- No deposit.

04/07/2023 - ST-022-NiCu-EtOH- Step test with Copper cathode

Objective

- See if using a copper cathode instead of the nickel cathode can lead to a more stable current or a better depolymerization
- Obtain less deposit with diluted BL than with copper cathode and undiluted BL

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7.5 mL Water + 7.5 mL WL + 5 mL Ethanol)

Cell : raw Ni anode, raw Cu cathode

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 108°C

Treal (bottle) = 74.8°C

Comments

Very big deposit on the cathode.

Samples

0V, 2V, tf

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- Too much deposit.
- Unstable current, especially for 2.25V where the current decreases over time.

05/07/2023 - ST-023-NiCu-Pro- Step test with Copper cathode

Objective

- See if using a copper cathode instead of the nickel cathode can lead to a more stable current or a better depolymerization
- Obtain less deposit with diluted BL than with copper cathode and undiluted BL

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7.5 mL Water + 7.5 mL WL + 5 mL 1-Propanol)

Cell : raw Ni anode, raw Cu cathode

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 108°C

Treal (bottle) = 74.8°C

Comments

Very big deposit on the cathode.

Samples

0V, 2V, tf

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- Too much deposit.
- Very unstable current, even for 2V.

06/07/2023 - ST-024-NiPb- Step test with Lead cathode

Objective

- See if using a lead (Pb) cathode instead of the nickel cathode can lead to a more stable current or a better depolymerization
- Obtain less deposit than with Cu cathode.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 10 mL Water + 10 mL WL)

Cell : raw Ni anode, raw Pb cathode

Sequence : “Step test V2 with the right sets”

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 135°C

Treal (bottle) = 90.2°C

Comments

Little deposit.

Samples

0V, 2V, tf

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- Very low current, “fuzzy” and not very stable above 2V.

07/07/2023 - ST-025-NiPb-EtOH- Step test with Lead cathode

Objective

- See if using a lead (Pb) cathode instead of the nickel cathode can lead to a more stable current or a better depolymerization
- Obtain less deposit than with Cu cathode.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7.5 mL Water + 7.5 mL WL + 5 mL Ethanol)

Cell : raw Ni anode, raw Pb cathode

Sequence : "Step test V2 with the right sets"

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 108°C

Treal (bottle) = 74.5°C

Comments

Little deposit.

Samples

0V, 2V, tf

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- Very low current and unstable even at 2V.

11/07/2023 - ST-026-NiPb-Pro- Step test with Lead cathode

Objective

- See if using a lead (Pb) cathode instead of the nickel cathode can lead to a more stable current or a better depolymerization
- Obtain less deposit than with Cu cathode.

Parameters

Reservoir : 40 mL (20 mL BL + 7.5 mL Water + 7.5 mL WL + 5 mL 1-Propanol)

Cell : raw Ni anode, raw Pb cathode

Sequence : “Step test V2 with the right sets”

- Duration : 3h
- Range : 1-2.25 V with 80 min at 2.25 V (last step)
- Sets : 0.02 V, 2 A

Temperature : Tset (oil) = 108°C

Treal (bottle) = 76.3°C

Comments

Little deposit.

Samples

0V, 2V, tf

Results

(See figure opposite)

Conclusion

- Very low current and unstable even at 2V.

 13/07/2023 – Comparing the step tests of different metals

The previous step tests are found in the following recap table:

Date exp.	Reference	Cathode	Electrolyte	Ratio electrolyte	T bottle (°C)	Deposit
30/06/2023	ST-020-NiCu-BL-W-WL	Cu	BL:W:WL	2:1:1	90,3	Yes
03/07/2023	ST-021-NiNi-BL-W-WL	Ni	BL:W:WL	2:1:1	90,3	No
04/07/2023	ST-022-NiCu-EtOH	Cu	BL:W:WL:EtOH	2:0,75:0,75:0,5	74,8	Yes (big)
05/07/2023	ST-023-NiCu-Pro	Cu	BL:W:WL:Pro	2:0,75:0,75:0,5	74,8	Yes (big)
06/07/2023	ST-024-NiPb	Pb	BL:W:WL	2:1:1	90,2	Yes
07/07/2023	ST-025-NiPb-EtOH	Pb	BL:W:WL:EtOH	2:0,75:0,75:0,5	74,5	Yes
11/07/2023	ST-026-NiPb-Pro	Pb	BL:W:WL:Pro	2:0,75:0,75:0,5	76,3	Yes
	ST-027-NiSS	SS	BL:W:WL	2:1:1		
	ST-028-NiSS-EtOH	SS	BL:W:WL:EtOH	2:0,75:0,75:0,5		
	ST-029-NiSS-Pro	SS	BL:W:WL:Pro	2:0,75:0,75:0,5		

Results

They have led to the following results: (Stainless steel cathode have not been tested yet):

(see following pages)

In the 3 following graphs, the different **metals** are compared for each dilution (with alcohol):

In the 3 following graphs, the different **dilutions** (with alcohols) are compared for each metal:

General comparison (all metals, all dilutions)

As seen on the graph, Cu cathodes lead to very high and unstable currents, and Pb cathodes lead to very low and “fuzzy” currents.

Conclusion

- At this point, it seems that Ni cathode do the best job at keeping stable and relatively high currents.
- Adding no alcohol, 1-propanol or ethanol does not have a big impact on the current, so the samples have to be analyzed in GC and HPLC to determine the impact on depolymerization of lignin.
- Stainless steel cathodes still need to be tested.